

ARTS

NATIONAL ARCHITECTURAL CULTURE OF NAKHCHIVAN

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Abstract

Every people, every nation with a history lasting for many millennia, with a powerful and rich past, has its own national values. National values are the best qualities that distinguish peoples, nations, societies from others. The national values of our people, which have a national root and a national foundation, are sufficient. In the aesthetic culture of medieval Azerbaijan and Nakhchivan, architecture, decorative applied art, and miniature art are a valuable resource as carriers of socio-philosophical meaning. Among the peoples of the world, the people of Azerbaijan, known for their national and spiritual values, occupy a unique place with their national characteristics, the human ideas and traditions that they live and propagate.

Keywords: architectural culture, ornament, harmony, philosophical meaning, symbol

Since ancient Nakhchivan is historically located on the great Silk Road, it has always been in the center of attention with its material and spiritual wealth. It has been known for centuries as an important craft, trade and cultural center in the Near and Middle East. That is why Nakhchivan is called the "Gate of the East". Every people, every nation with a history lasting for many millennia, with a powerful and rich past, has its own national values. National values are the best qualities that distinguish peoples, nations, societies from others. The national values of the Azerbaijani people, who have a national root and a national foundation, are sufficient from its language, religion, music, folklore, to its world-famous personalities. In this sense, we can talk at length about the national values of our people. Among the peoples of the world, the people of Azerbaijan, known for their national and spiritual values, occupy a unique place with their national characteristics, the human ideas and traditions that they live and propagate.

Although Nakhchivan became one of the major cities of Azerbaijan in the early Middle Ages, the volume of construction works rose to a level never seen before in the second half of the 12th century and the beginning of the 13th century.

Known as the last stop of Prophet Noah's ark, Kapjik Peak of Nakhchivan means the small door that opens to the new life of humanity. Gemigaya images are an integral part of the Bronze Age culture of Nakhchivan. The belief in the Sky, which is figuratively expressed in the images of Gamigaya, the concepts of this world and the other world, are traced in the mythology of the Turkic peoples. This way of thinking continues to live in the works of art of the Azerbaijani people, folklore and ethnographic materials. The ancient Eastern culture, especially the Sumerian culture, had a certain influence on the formation of the mythological meetings of the ancient tribes living in the territory of Azerbaijan. This influence manifests itself in the depictions of Gamigaya, as well as in other archaeological monuments [6,p.70].

The land of Nakhchivan has been known in the Middle East for its rare architectural examples since ancient times. Remains of mudbrick and seal buildings belonging to the ancient architecture of Nakhchivan in settlements belonging to the end of the 3rd millennium BC and the beginning of the 2nd millennium BC, and the remains of the city sites surrounded by magnificent fortress walls with rectangular and semi-circular towers in the territory of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic have survived to this day.

I Kultepa, the ancient city center of Nakhchivan, Ovchulug hill, etc. discovered pottery quarters, mudbrick spheres, and a large amount of farm and household utensils prove that the art of pottery reached a high level here. In this period, the potters of Nakhchivan not only produced agricultural and household items of various purposes, but also achieved important achievements in their painting.

During the archeological excavations carried out in the above-mentioned housing areas, red, black, gray, brown and other colors were used in painting of discovered jugs, bowls, glasses, etc. During the artistic design of the pottery products of this period, the methods of drawing, making, drawing, and stapling were widely used [3, p. 139].

Nakhchivan city is one of the most important centers of the ancient urban culture, which was formed in the III millennium BC, and the fact that the Iron Age settlements have a magnificent defense system confirms that the tribes living in this area have great economic power.

The settlements of Nakhchivan belonging to different historical periods are interesting with their wealth of cyclopean buildings, monuments of material culture and architecture, castles, fortifications, construction materials, and construction equipment.

In the 12th century, Nakhchivan, the capital of the mighty Atabay state, was one of the centers of high culture and craftsmanship in the Near and Middle East, and reached a high level in the field of architectural art. It includes numerous religious architectural monuments and civil buildings, magnificent mosques decorated with rich ornaments and paints, tombs, palaces,

inns, bridges, castles and towers, madrasas, ornate residential houses, baths with perfect architectural structure.

The architectural monuments created by Ajami Abubakr oglu Nakhchivani, the great architect of the medieval Muslim East, representative of the Nakhchivan school of architecture, rose to the level of the peak of the development of Muslim architecture in that period and had a decisive influence on the formation of the architecture that followed him. Ajami architectural examples, whose structure and forms are based on the eternal living laws of harmony, show us the attractive power of their divine beauty even today. In this period, which we call the classical period, the Islamic world was a world where science and intellectual life were very bright. Understanding the divine art, the obvious beauties in this art, the harmony of the material and spiritual values that form the basis of our existence, beauty embracing perfection, and perfection embracing beauty, was a world of magic. In this period, the Islamic culture, which took its source from two main sources: from science, which is a material source, and from the virtues and moral dimensions of Islam, which is a spiritual source, opened the greatest scientific discovery horizon, which led to the development of the high aspects of the old cultures. Among those who gave these pearls during the formation of Ajami architecture, genius representatives of artistic-aesthetic, scientific and philosophical ideas of the Middle Ages Muslim East, Khagani Shirvani, Abulhasan Bahmanyar, Shihabeddin Maragai, Nizami Ganjavi, etc., took an exceptional place. This world, which preserved its vitality and brightness for five centuries, has left priceless legacies to the modern age [2, p. 8].

Corresponding member of ANAS, doctor of architecture Jafar Ghiyasi, talking about medieval Azerbaijani architectural forms, shows that "Medieval Azerbaijani architecture was based on the canons common to all Muslim architecture, a single scientific theoretical system. As this union is self-evident in various fields of construction art, it manifests itself in the form of decorating surfaces with patterns in architectural decoration. The use of patterns in architectural decoration in this period in an unprecedented abundance was related to the strong demand for decorativeness and symbolism in the arts of the time"[1,p.185].

The national architectural culture of Nakhchivan was formed in the Middle Ages and has changed very little. As in all of Azerbaijan, our national moral values in Nakhchivan were formed under the influence of moral rules, which are often called Turkish-Islamic values.

Medieval national architectural culture of Nakhchivan covers the most diverse events. From the earliest times to the present day, the local population living in the territory of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic has shown a strong inclination towards well-maintained objects, and they have not remained indifferent to flowers, gardens, patterns, beautiful forms, and awe-inspiring decorations. The people living here chose certain forms, signs, omens, marks to express certain content in their behavior and art, and considered them as characteristics of beauty.

It is known that before the era, patterns of life were various decorations, dishes, and weapons, but in our millennium, they are mainly architectural monuments. Of course, in the Middle Ages, as in the whole of Azerbaijan, in Nakhchivan, as an ancient tradition, the application of patterns in household items and the elaboration of them in our folk art continued as before. Our architectural monuments, which have kept our ornamental art alive until now, are mosques, minarets, domes, tombs, inns and so on. Those monuments have found the solution of beauty with maximum simplicity by staying true to their functions and traditions, and adapting to the environment. This was another form of performance of the poetry of that time.

The same line of development manifests itself in patterns. The formation and development of ancient and medieval Nakhchivan decorative-applied art continues to be preserved even now in the decorations of decorative applied art examples created at that time. In the inscriptions on the medieval Nakhchivan architectural examples and on the examples of decorative applied art, verses of the Koran and poetic sayings were included in the patterns, the ornament did not become meaningless.

The prominent American historian of Islamic culture, Will Durant, who talks about this fact playing a leading role in the medieval Muslim Eastern architecture, shows that "Muslim artists used mosaics, carved flowers and inscriptions, colored marble, and bricks to beautify the mihrab with all their skills. The popularity of this art is probably due to the ban on the depiction of animal and human images. Islamic art invented an extremely diverse composition of figures to overcome this deficiency. First, he took advantage of geometric figures: He used lines, angles, squares, cubes, cones, spirals, ellipses, spheres, polygons, triangles. These were formed with each other in the form of countless compositions and formed many images. Then it turned to flowers, using various means to take advantage of the flower forms. In the 10th century, they did all this in arabesque forms. And above all, they used writing, which is the highest decorative element. In particular, he used the Kufic line, raised, spread, expanded the letters, or made the alphabet an art tool by decorating it with dots and lines [5.p.132]. Indeed, in the first stages of development, geometric patterns prevailed, and in later periods, the development of vegetable patterns prevailed.

Calligraphy also had the purpose of decoration. A friendly union between writing and painting is known from ancient Chinese sources. Kufi script from Kufa was skillfully worked by calligraphers and made into a composition with flowers and other patterns. Thus, the Kufic script became one of the main decorative elements of the architecture of that time. In the later period, linear writing (Nasihaliq) began to be used in the decor of architectural and historical monuments. In no part of the world could there be more beautiful writing and a more beautiful art created from these writings [4.p.88]. Thus, writing motifs made from Arabic graphics found their decorative solution in all architectural and artistic works of the period.

In the aesthetic culture of medieval Azerbaijan, as well as Nakhchivan, architecture, decorative applied art, and miniature art had socio-philosophical meaning. In miniatures, color absorbs light, becomes transparent, and shines without shadows. In the miniatures, the light seems to be resolved by one color, the expression of the spatial values falls under the responsibility of the color, and the aerial perspective is eliminated. Patterns complementing the images were applied in abundance in this art. Among those who gave these pearls during the formation of miniature art were miniaturist Soltan Muhammad, Kamaladdin Behzad, Abdulmomin Muhammad al-Khoyi, Mirza Ali, Muzaffar Ali, Sadiq Bey Afshar, etc, occupied an exceptional place.

The widespread spread of ornamental art in the Muslim countries of the Near and Middle East, as well as in Nakhchivan, and the attempts to turn the ornament into a meaningful sign by moving from ornament to writing, from writing to ornament, created a philosophical meaning in the patterns. As researchers have shown, the geometric patterns created in this period can be considered an integral form for the spirit of Islam. Ceremonies, which are a branch of national moral values, are repeated rhythmically in the public space, and certain patterns remain unchanged in patterns, which

reflects the synthesis of our national moral values. Thus, ornamental art in all Muslim countries, including Nakhchivan, is connected to serious socio-philosophical roots. Researchers see geometric shapes as symbols of absolute existence. The fact that ornaments, which are part of the national architectural culture of Nakhchivan, are often repeated in science as symbols of religious and philosophical meanings is a fundamental issue of our architectural theory.

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CREATIVE ATTITUDE TO MINIATURE AESTHETICS

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Abstract

The sixties-eighties stage of Azerbaijani painting, which has an ancient history and rich artistic traditions, was also characterized by appeals to national traditions by artists of different ages. One of such creators was Yuran Mammadov (1934-1984), who lived and created in Nakhchivan. The young artist who studied in Baku and St. Petersburg and is deeply familiar with the traditions of realism, unlike many others, preferred to create paintings with modern themes and different genres with a creative attitude to the miniature style, which has ancient traditions. Yuran Mammadov, who tried himself in the art of painting, graphics and theater decoration in his 22-year career, left behind him an artistic heritage that could literally enrich the 20th century Azerbaijani fine art. "Afternoon", "By the spring" and "Portrait of my son", a creative approach to the aesthetics of the classic miniature style can be heard in the paintings. This can be observed both in the artistic solution of the works and in the use of contrasting shades of colors that give the compositions a national flavor.

Keywords: classic, tradition, miniature, contrast, heritage, aesthetics, theme, genre.

Since the teaching process in the first art school established in Baku after the occupation of Azerbaijan by the 11th Army was conducted on the basis of the artistic principle of "socialist realism" corresponding to the Soviet ideology, the students created their creative examples directly by following the traditions of realism. Despite this, the school's young graduates also showed an example of returning to their roots - benefiting from the miniature style - in their post-educational pursuits. This was considered to be a direct reflection of the desire to deviate from the demands of the "tops" - Kremlin ideologues. Therefore, it was expected that it would not go unanswered. In the exhibition held in Baku in 1934 on the occasion of the 1000th anniversary of the birth of such a famous poet Ferdovsi, the works by young Azerbaijani artists (Alekbard Rzagaluyev,

Salam Salamzade, Gazanfar Khaligov, Amir Hajiyev, etc.) were criticized for returning to the ancient artistic tradition. When recalling the repression of the thirties, it can be considered understandable that the others, except for A.Rzagaluyev, moved away from the miniature [2]. A. Rzagaluyev's 28 years of exile and prison life after that can be considered as an image of the current regime's attitude towards this issue. However, it should be said that the miniature style, which has been confirmed for a long time, has become a reliable moral support for the artistic pursuits of several Azerbaijani artists even in the historicized 20th century. It is a good thing that the artists of Nakhchivan have from time to time creatively benefited from this timeless style and have created works of various genres that bring to life